

Technical note describing the updates of the HARMONIE-AROME system

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1. Nordic NWP HARMONIE-AROME use of satellite passive microwave radiances at start of ESA project

1.1 Organisation of NWP

The four Nordic countries, Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden, all base their local regional Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) systems on a common framework. This framework is based on a configuration of A Consortium for Convection-Scale Modeling Research and Development (ACCORD) common modelling system. ACCORD is a consortium of 26 countries in Europe and northern Africa developing advanced, high-resolution weather prediction capability for local areas. The code base is shared with the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Integrated Forecasting System (IFS). The ACCORD forecasting system can be run with different configurations; in the nordic countries, the HIRLAM–ALADIN Research on Mesoscale Operational NWP in Europe–Application of Research to Operations at Mesoscale (HARMONIE–AROME; Bengtsson et al., 2017) is used. For the Nordic countries, HARMONIE-AROME is the main modelling tool and with a reference system, including both source code and scripts. This reference system, maintained by the HIRLAM (High Resolution Limited Area Modelling) sub-consortium, containing common source code and scripts, forms the basis for the local NWP implementations and operational settings in the Nordic countries. The reference system is prepared for utilising various types of observations for building the limited-area model initial state. These include various types of satellite based measurement such as passive MicroWave (MW), Infrared (IR), passive radiances, scatterometer derived winds, GNSS radio occultations (RO) and atmospheric motion vectors (AMVs). Sweden, Norway, Finland and Estonia shared a common operational system named MetCoOp. Currently, Denmark has a common operational system with Iceland but the operational collaboration will be extended to also include Ireland and the Netherlands. This four country collaboration, called United Weather Centers West (UWC-west) is planned to start in 2023 and to be based on the system outlined above. UWC-west is planned to merge with MetCoOp in 2028. Figure 1 shows the current operational MetCoOp domain (left), the current operational Danish/Icelandic domains (middle) and the planned UWC-west domains (right). Together with the MetCoOp domain we show the AROME-ARCTIC domain, which is run by the Norwegian meteorological service over the Arctic with rather similar microwave radiance observation usage to MetCoOp. All currently operational configurations apply a 2.5 km horizontal grid-distance and use 65 vertical levels. For UWC-west use of 90 vertical levels are planned in operations.

Figure 1. MetCoOp and AROME-ARCTIC current operational model domains (left), Danish/Icelandic

operational model domains (middle) and planned UWC-west domains (right).

Some minor differences in model set-up and observation usage currently exist between the countries due to slight differences in the priorities, infrastructures, person-months, etc. There is however work towards reducing these minor differences and ultimately to have one common Nordic operational NWP system.

The relations between ECMWF, ACCORD, HIRLAM and Nordic operational regional NWP systems are graphically illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Relation between Nordic operational NWP systems and ACCORD development consortium. Grey rectangles represent organisations/consortia/centres and white ellipses code basis and NWP systems.

1.2 Current use of MW radiances

Use of MW satellite observations has been demonstrated to be important both in global and limited-area data assimilation (Geer et al., 2017; Storto and Randriamampianina, 2010, Randriamampianina et al., 2019, Lindskog et. al. 2021). The reference system (cy43) is at European Space Agency (ESA) Arctic Weather Satellite (AWS) project start is prepared for MW usage from MHS (Microwave Humidity Sounder), AMSU-A (Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit), ATMS (Advanced Technology Microwave Sounder), MWHS-2 (Micro-Wave Humidity Sounder-2) instruments onboard NOAA-POES, Metop, Feng-Yun-3 and Suomi-NPP/JPSS satellites. Concerning MW in HARMONIE-AROME a clear-sky approach is currently applied. To indicate whether radiance data from particular instruments and channels are affected by clouds, radiances in associated window channels within the instrument, capable of identifying clouds, are compared with the corresponding model state equivalents. If the window channel departures are larger than a particular threshold value, the corresponding non-window channel radiances are considered to be affected by clouds, and are therefore rejected from use in the DA. For some rather high-peaking channels, no cloud detection is applied and for some other channels, a complementary check, aiming at identifying cloud and rain, is applied, using liquid water path and scattering index. In case of too high liquid water path or enhanced scattering from precipitation-sized particles, radiance observations from these channels are considered contaminated by large hydrometeors and are therefore rejected. For further details see Lindskog et al. (2021) .

The default HARMONIE-AROME atmospheric data assimilation methodology is 3-dimensional

variational data assimilation (Fischer et al., 2005). Also a 4-dimensional variational assimilation (Barkmeijer et al., 2021; Courtier et al., 1994; Gustafsson et al., 2012) system exists as an option. Still in the research environment, ensemble-based data assimilation methods are being explored. The achievements regarding enhanced use of MW radiances from heritage instruments will be built on and further refined when preparing for and exploiting the use of AWS (Lagaune et al., 2021; Albers et al., 2023) traditionally used channels (legacy channels).

At ESA AWS project start in December 2021, both MetCoOp and Denmark/Iceland utilised operationally microwave radiances from the MHS and AMSU-A instruments on-board the NOAA-POES and Metop polar orbiting satellites. In addition Denmark/Iceland have prepared for assimilation of radiances from ATMS on-board the Suomi-NPP polar orbiting satellite. MetCoOp on the other hand has gained experience from the MWHS-2 on-board FY-3C and FY-3D satellites. Thus there are some respective sharing of developments needed for both of the operational systems and that will also feed back to the HARMONIE-AROME reference system. There is a need to upgrade the Danish/Icelandic, AROME-Arctic, the MetCoOp operational systems, and the HARMONIE-AROME reference system to use microwave radiances from the new sensors orography@modsurfon-board the EPS-SG-A and B-platforms (Microwave Sounder-MWS on the A-platform and IceCloudImager-ICI and MicroWave Imager-MWI on the B-platform). Observation cut-off time is around 1 h in all operational systems mentioned above. The use of satellite radiances at project start (clear-sky only), December 2021, in the operational systems are summarised in Table 1 below. For MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic the same instruments and channels as used over sea are also used over sea-ice. In DMI settings there is a more restrictive use of radiances over sea-ice. This is an area where we foresee harmonisation of improvements in future versions.

Table 1. MW data usage in MetCoOp, AROME-ARCTIC and DMI operational DA (N18=NOAA-18, N19=NOAA-19, SNP=Suomi NPP, MA=Metop-A, MB=Metop-B, MC=Metop-C, FY3D=FY-3D) at project start (December, 2021).

	N18	N19	SNP	MA	MB	MC	FY3D	land/sea	land	open sea	Sea ice
AMSU-A	xxx	xxx		x	xxx	xx		6-9, 5-9, 5-10	6-9,5-9	6-9, 5-9,5-10	6-9, 5-9,7-10
ATMS			x					5-9,17-22	7-9,17-22	5-9,17-22	7-9,17
MHS		xx		x	xxx	xx		3-5, 3-5	3-4,3-4,3-4	3-5,3-5,3-5	3-5, 3-5, none
MWHS-2							x	4-6,11-15	4-6,11-14	4-6,11-15	4-6,11-15

1.3 Plans for enhanced use of MW radiances

Within this project we have prepared an AWS branch of the HARMONIE-AROME modelling system for use of data from the MW instrument on the AWS satellite. These preparations are described in Section 2 below. In addition to these preparations, research and several enhancements with respect to general use of MW radiances in the HARMONIE-AROME modelling system has been carried out. These are for an improved use of MW radiances also from heritage instruments. Like the technical preparations for use of AWS instrument data, these general enhancements have already been or will be made available for the operational Nordic HARMONIE-AROME limited area modelling configurations as described above. The general enhancements are described in Section 3 below and include (1) an enhanced use of low-peaking MW channels, (2) use of footprint operator for a refined handling of spatial scale differences between observation and forecast model and (3) work towards future use of satellite radiances during all-sky conditions. Project work and results are presented in Section 3 of this report. It also covers our preparations in the

HARMONIE-AROME NWP systems for use of 325 GHz frequency radiances from the AWS instrument. Finally a summary of ESA AWS project HARMONIE-AROME developments and their implication for Nordic limited-area NWP are summarised in Section 4.

2. Technical preparations for handling of AWS data

The future operational use of data from the AWS satellite and later on from the EPS-Sterna constellation relies on that the code developments made here are propagated in the proper fashion to future model versions and become beneficial to all users of the HARMONIE-AROME model, especially the nordic operational applications.

In the AWS project, we have created a new branch `AWS_branch@git` (accessible at <https://github.com/dschoenach/Harmonie/tree/feature/AWS-developments-WP2.1>) in a fork of the HIRLAM code repository. This branch is based on HIRLAM's `harmonie-43h2.2` version (found at <https://github.com/Hirlam/Harmonie/releases/tag/harmonie-43h2.2>). The operational configurations of MetCoOp, AROME-ARCTIC and DMI are all currently based on modelling cycle 43. The chosen cycle version, `cy43h2.2`, shows stable behaviour in both research and operational environments. The `AWS_branch@git` is accessible to and utilised by the ESA AWS project work packages (WPs). All code modifications related to the AWS project will be incorporated into this branch, with the intention of committing these changes to the original HIRLAM code repository mainly progressively and in some cases upon project completion.

Preparation of the HARMONIE-AROME system to ingest AWS radiances can be divided into two steps: *Step 1*, converting the AWS radiance data into internal model Observations Database (ODB) format. *Step 2*, adjusting the HARMONIE-AROME data assimilation system to read the ODB, set observation errors, perform quality control and variational bias-correction, call the fast radiative transfer model RTTOV (Radiative Transfer for TOVS; Saunders et al., 2018) to get model equivalents to the observed brightness temperatures. For *step 1* one would ideally want some kind of sample file with AWS radiances that has the same format and structure as the real data will have when the satellite is in orbit. In our case, it was a NetCDF file with sample MWS data. The observation pre-processing tool in HARMONIE-AROME to convert input observations in various formats to ODB, and prepare for assimilation, is called BATOR. We have developed a NetCDF interface that reads a sample file with MWS radiances and writes these observations into ODB. This interface can be extended to read AWS data in NetCDF format when that becomes available¹. In the meantime data in ASCII will be used that contains synthetic AWS radiances. These ASCII files come from the Eumetsat AWS project EPS-Sterna, where an Observing System Simulation Experiment (OSSE) with AWS is being prepared. For the OSSE, a number of orbit scenarios were provided that gives the time and position of the footprints in the orbit scenarios. We have converted the orbit scenario files to ASCII and developed a BATOR interface that creates an ODB from these

¹ A first sample NetCDF data file for AWS became available on the 23rd of August 2023. The data contains one full orbit with realistic simulated geolocation but radiances were not realistic for an earth scene (contained observations made while scanning in the clean room). With the help of the NWPSAF this sample file was tweaked by adding realistic earth scene observations simulated with RTTOV, and this file was made available to the project in September 2023, thanks to Nigel Atkinson, UK Met Office. However this was almost a year behind schedule. As work was started in spring 2023 preparing the technical interfaces an alternative solution had to be pursued, as this work could not be delayed any further waiting for test data to be provided by ESA.

files. In the OSSE, the same interface is also used and much of the technical work in *step 2* has already been done as the OSSE needs to call RTTOV to compute synthetic radiances from the nature run. Many of these developments can be ported into the AWS code branch. The synthetic radiances from the OSSE will not be useful for us since an OSSE is based on an idealised framework where the nature run represents the truth (it is a long forecast integration with the Météo-France global ARPEGE model). We will instead use the OSSE tools and replace the nature run with HARMONIE-AROME model fields which will be used to compute AWS radiances with RTTOV. Then we perturb the radiances and use them as synthetic observations. To facilitate the assimilation of AWS radiances in HARMONIE-AROME one needs to include the AWS definitions in a couple of arrays inside the code so that these novel data are recognized by the data assimilation system. Then the data will follow the same path through the source code as other microwave data such as AMSU-A, MHS and ATMS. Inside the data assimilation system the observation errors are set (defrun.F90) and the so called blacklist file is called where general settings such as e.g. which channels to assimilate are defined. Then RTTOV is called to get model equivalents of the observed radiances and after that quality control, including spatial thinning, is done. Quality control includes comparing the distance between observation and background (i.e. model equivalents) and reject if too large. The limits for rejection are set (defrun.F90). The quality control also includes satellite specific controls such as checking for clouds and rain. As a first step AWS uses the same controls as AMSU-A and MHS but we will later change these for AWS specific controls described below. VARIational Bias Correction (VARBC; Dee, 2005) is also applied before entering the minimization where the analysis is being created.

The general enhancements described below regarding use of low peaking channels and use of a footprint operator will be adapted also to AWS. The preparations rely on a pre-remapping of the channels to common horizontal positions. In addition we are preparing for use of 325 GHz channel radiances for improved cloud detection.

3. General enhancements regarding use of MW radiances

3.1 Handling of surface-sensitive low-peaking MW channels

3.1.1 General idea

The contribution from the surface to the total emitted radiance can be significant at some frequencies and this might represent a large source of uncertainties. In fact, to assimilate a radiance, the first criteria must be to be able to properly simulate the model equivalent to the observed brightness temperature. For a local satellite zenith angle θ of observation and a frequency ν , the model equivalent of the brightness temperature, T_b , observed by a sensor can be expressed as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} T_b(\theta) &= T_s \varepsilon(\theta) \Gamma + (1 - \varepsilon(\theta)) \Gamma T_a^\downarrow(\theta) + T_a^\uparrow(\theta) \\ \Gamma &= \exp\left(\frac{-\tau(0,H)}{\cos(\theta)}\right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $\varepsilon(\theta)$ represents the surface emissivity and T_s , $T_a\downarrow(\theta)$, and $T_a\uparrow(\theta)$ are the skin temperature and the atmospheric down-welling and upwelling T_b , respectively. The net atmospheric transmissivity Γ is expressed as a function of the atmospheric opacity $\tau(0, H)$ and the observation zenith angle θ . H is the top-of-atmosphere height.

Presently, within the preprocessing chain of HARMONIE-AROME, the surface temperature is provided by using the Surface Externalisée (SURFEX) scheme (Masson et al., 2013). The sea surface temperature (SST) is taken from the ECMWF IFS, which, in turn, provides a product based on the Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA, Donlon et al., 2012) from the UK Met Office. The surface emissivity is based on FASTEM-4 (FAST microwave Emissivity Model) over sea surfaces. Over land, a classification-based emissivity scheme (Weng et al., 2001 and Grody, 1988) is used for AMSU-A (50 GHz's channels) and a constant value for MHS (183 GHz's channels):

- exposed dry land $\Rightarrow \varepsilon = 0.92$
- exposed moist land or light snow cover $\Rightarrow \varepsilon = 0.95$
- exposed deep snow cover \Rightarrow if $T_s < 265$ $\varepsilon = 0.83$ else $\varepsilon = 0.95$
- exposed very deep snow cover \Rightarrow if $T_s < 265$ $\varepsilon = 0.8$ else $\varepsilon = 0.95$

Because the uncertainties on the land surface temperature and emissivity are very high, the response has so far been to reject/discard all surface-sensitive observations where large systematic departures can exist, without considering whether the observation or the model is primarily responsible. In the next sections, we explore methodologies to overcome this limitation and enable the use of additional low-peaking channels in the microwave to improve the forecast skill of our regional system.

There are various ways to handle the surface emissivities. The method taken here for short term operational use is to introduce a so-called dynamical emissivity approach, described in section 3.1.2. In our reference settings a specular assumption of land surface reflection is applied (Guedj et al. 2010), but also introduction of Lambertian emissivity representation over snow and ice is being investigated, as presented in 3.1.3. As a longer term-preparation and as an alternative to the dynamical emissivity approach we are in addition exploiting the derivation of emissivity products applying statistical estimation theory combining satellite observations with other observations and models, as presented in 3.1.4. The forecast impact of the proposed enhancements for the currently used MW sounders are presented in section 3.1.5.

3.1.2 Dynamical emissivity approach

The HARMONIE-AROME AWS branch has been prepared for enhanced use of MW radiances as compared to operational Nordic HARMONIE-AROME NWP system status at project start. These enhancements include use of AMSU-A channel 5 over all surfaces, MHS channel 5 over all surfaces, ATMS channels 6 and 18 over all surfaces as well as MWHS-2 channel 11 over all surfaces. Over all surfaces we here refer to over, sea, land, and sea-ice. The approach followed was to introduce and apply a dynamical estimation of surface emissivity contributions to these low peaking channels (Karbou et al. 2006; Guedj et al., 2010; Bormann et.al., 2017). The basic idea is to derive the surface emissivity from a nearby window-channel, not so much influenced by the atmospheric state. Thus, ε is estimated from a nearby window channel, which allowed for assimilation of additional low peaking channels, as compared to the reference system before project start. The additional channels included and their associated window channels used in the dynamical

emissivity approach are presented in Table 2. For the AWS instrument it will be natural to use the 50.3 GHz channel for estimating ϵ for temperature sounding channels in the frequency band around 55 GHz and the 89 GHz channel for estimating ϵ for humidity sounding channels in the frequency band around 183 GHz.

Table 2. Enhanced usage of low peaking channels from heritage channels and associated window channels.

Instrument	Channel numbers of the new channels assimilated	Central Frequencies of new channels assimilated (GHz)	Frequency of Window channel (GHz)
AMSU-A	5	53.596 \pm 0.115	52.8
ATMS	6,18	53.596 \pm 0.115, 183.31 \pm 7.0	52,8; 88.2
MHS	5 over land	190.311	89
MWHS-2	11 over land	183.31 \pm 7.0	89

In the following, we will give more details on the method and assumptions used to retrieve the emissivity in our AWS branch. Instead of using the default HARMONIE-AROME emissivity over land, one can use “effective” surface emissivity retrievals, as described in Karbou and Prigent (2005). Assuming 1) a non-scattering and plane parallel atmosphere, 2) a specular reflexion over the surface in $T_{\downarrow a}(\nu, \theta)$, 3) the medium emits at the temperature of the surface skin and 4) the variability of emissivity with frequency is low, the emissivity can be retrieved, at windows channels frequencies, and allocated to adjacent sounding channels, reversing the radiative transfer equation 1 by:

$$\epsilon(\nu, \theta) = \frac{T_b(\nu, \theta) - T_a^\uparrow(\nu, \theta) - T_a^\downarrow(\nu, \theta) \Gamma}{(T_s - T_a^\downarrow(\nu, \theta)) \Gamma} \quad (2)$$

The emissivity is retrieved at each observation point, prior to the T_b simulation. Together with the T_s provided by the HARMONIE-AROME background, emissivity retrievals are used over land to simulate the T_b in a dynamical way (i.e. updated continuously) and in a consistent way with the instrument characteristic (resolution, geometry etc.). In this study, the emissivity retrieved at AMSU-A channel 3 (MHS channel 1) is allocated to AMSU-A channel 4 to 9 (MHS channel 3 to 5).

Also, when the atmospheric transmission is lower than 0.5 at window and low-peaking channels, the dynamical estimation of emissivity is not performed to avoid too noisy emissivity retrievals. It regards less than 0.1% of the cases since the surface transmittance is high at Northern latitudes (see Table 3).

Table 3. Mean (standard deviation) of atmospheric transmittance at the surface for radiances at AMSU-A and MHS window channels (data from 2021/02/10-09 UTC and 2021/06/10-09 UTC).

	AMSU-A Channel 3	MHS Channel 1	MHS channel 2
summer	0.66 (0.03)	0.77 (0.06)	0.46 (0.11)
winter	0.66 (0.03)	0.90 (0.02)	0.84 (0.05)

In this case, emissivities from a monthly emissivity atlas are used over land surfaces or static emissivity is taken for sea-ice. Atlases were kindly provided by Météo-France. Monthly maps were computed using observations from 2015 together with short-range forecasts of the global ARPEGE model. In the context of the dynamic emissivity method, the cloud/rain contamination of microwave observations is likely to occur (i.e. if cloud screening fails) and could explain part of the variability of the emissivity, resulting in larger observation departures to first guess or to analysis.

Figure 3 shows monthly mean emissivity maps at AMSU-A channel 3 (50 GHz) over land surfaces in the MetCoOp domain for a winter month of 2021. The CTL emissivity based on the methodology provided by Weng et al. (2001) and Grody (1988) show overall lower values compared to the ATLAS and LDYN for both periods. The amplitude of the difference with the CTL is about 20% for AMSU-A. One reason could be the presence of snow-covered surface changing the characteristics and the depth of the emitting layer. Cloudy observations contaminated by snow fall might also be another source of uncertainties which could impact the quality of the retrieval.

Figure 3. Average land surface emissivity maps at AMSU-A Channel 3 (50 GHz) for winter month 2021. HARMONIE-AROME default emissivity (CTL) on the left, monthly emissivity atlas (ATLAS) in the middle and averaged dynamical retrievals (LDYN) on the right side.

Handling of surface emissivities over sea-ice required some special handling in the form of an extrapolation in frequency-space, following Karbou et al. (2014). This technique is and associated results are also further described in 3.1.3.

The level of uncertainties on the retrieval can be very high over heterogeneous pixels that comprise, for example, a portion of land with high emissivity mixed with a portion of sea where the emissivity is significantly lower. In order to overcome that limitation and reduce these representativeness errors, we explore in section 3.2 a way to further improve the simulation of low-peaking channel observations.

3.1.3 Special handling over sea-ice and snow

Following the dynamical emissivity approach, sea-ice emissivity at humidity sensitive frequencies around 183 GHz have been retrieved following Karbou et al. (2014). For MHS, the emissivity is retrieved at channel 1 (89 GHz) and propagated at channel 2 (157 GHz) using a linear regression method as follow:

$$\varepsilon(157, \theta)_{extr} = \varepsilon(89, \theta) - \frac{T_b(157, \theta) - T_b(89, \theta)}{T_s} \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon(157, \theta)$ is the extrapolated emissivity at channel 2 (157GHz) computed using the retrieved emissivity at channel 1 ($\varepsilon(89, \theta)$) and the difference between observed brightness temperature at channel 1 and 2 ($T_b(157, \theta) - T_b(89, \theta)$) and the surface skin temperature from a short range forecast of HARMONIE-AROME T_s . Here θ represents the local satellite zenith angle of observation. The same approach is applied for ATMS. Over sea-ice, no pre-computed atlas is available from the 2015 database. In Figure 4, a comparison between the constant emissivity in CTL (left) for MHS channel 1 (89 GHz) and the emissivity retrieved in LDYN (right) configuration is given for a specific case in winter 2021. In the latter, the average emissivity is about 0.87 with a standard deviation approaching 0.06. Compared to the static sub-optimal value that is used in the CTL, one can see the benefit of using LDYN to capture more closely the variability of sea-ice emission.

Figure 4. Average sea-ice surface emissivity maps at MHS Channel 1 (89 GHz) in 20-21 February 2021. Left panel for HARMONIE-AROME default parameterisation and right panel with LDYN approach.

There is on-going work to investigate the assumption of specular reflection and to apply a Lambertian reflection as an alternative. The Lambertian reflection may be more accurate in areas of sea-ice and snow. The work follows ideas of Guedj et al. (2010). The difference between Lambertian and specular reflection assumptions is graphically illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Surface scattering: Lambertian (or diffuse) and specular (from Fig.2 in Guedj et al. (2010)).

One should note that (1) implies that the observation zenith angle is the same for incident and reflected radiations (see Fig. 5). In that case, the downwelling radiation can be expressed as:

$$T_a^\downarrow(\theta) = \int_H^0 T(z)\alpha(z)e^{-\tau(z,0)/\cos(\theta)} dz \quad (4)$$

For very rough surfaces which are characterised by Lambertian reflection, radiation is isotropically reflected by the surface (see Fig. 5), and the expression becomes:

$$T_a^\downarrow(\theta) = \int_0^{\pi/2} 2 \cos(\theta) \sin(\theta) \times \left(\int_H^0 T(z)\alpha(z)/\cos(\theta)e^{-\tau(z,0)/\cos(\theta)} dz \right) d\theta. \quad (5)$$

Current status of work is that the Lambertian reflection option has been activated in the HARMONIE-AROME modelling system, both with 3D-Var and 4D-Var, and is being explored in forward model simulations and some first assimilation experiments. In the following we illustrate some results from the 3D-Var framework. Figure 6 shows, as a function of scan position, an example of the difference between Specular and Lambertian assumptions in retrieved surface emissivity for AMSU-A channel 5 (50 GHz). Differences up to around 0.25 can be seen.

Figure 6. Scatterplot of 2-days emissivity retrievals at AMSU-A channel 3 (50 GHz) using Specular assumption minus retrievals using a Lambertian hypothesis. Results are plotted as a function scan positions (15 represents nadir) over land surfaces of the AROME-Arctic domain in February 2023.

As another example of recent results we show in Figure 7 for a 10 days assimilation experiment with dynamical emissivities activated a histogram of MHS channel 5 observation minus model departures using the retrieved emissivities, with specular reflection assumption (red) and with Lambertian reflection assumption (black) over snow-covered land surfaces. It can be seen that the reflection assumption has a clear effect on the observation minus model departures. Positive impact can be seen for all low-peaking AMSU-A and MHS channels over snow when using the Lambertian reflection in winter. However, the use of Lambertian approximation has shown some detrimental effect on sea ice (not shown).

Figure 7. Histograms of first guess departures (observation minus model equivalent) of MHS channel 5 close to nadir brightness temperatures for one single data assimilation cycle and with specular (red) and Lambertian (black) emissivity assumption.

Results and conclusions from first extended experiments with 3D-Var are presented in section 3.1.5. As a next step we plan investigations of most suitable settings of surface reflection assumptions and explore also possibilities for combined use of specular and Lambertian reflection. Results so far indicate that the currently used specular reflection option will likely remain in the HARMONIE-AROME system to be used at launch of AWS.

3.1.4 Longer term research of surface emissivity representation for future use in HARMONIE-AROME

Observation operators, providing the link between snow and sea ice and the radiances measured onboard satellites, have several important applications. These applications include integrated retrievals using statistical estimation theory of snow/ice and atmospheric parameters, noise reduction in for example sea ice concentration retrievals, combining satellite observations with other observations and models, and for assimilation, for example in this project, for sounding of the atmosphere.

In fact, from idealised experiments, accurate specification of sea ice emissivity in the numerical weather prediction (NWP) modelling has been emphasised in the improvement of analysis and forecast over the Arctic (Karbou et al., 2014).

Studies have been conducted to obtain the sea ice emissivity over the microwave spectrum, which may be used in NWP. English and Hewison (1998) designed an emissivity model based on Fresnel equation and dielectric permittivity (called FASTEM), consisting of sets of coefficients for 12 sea ice types under the dry snow conditions. The climatological monthly emissivity atlas (called TELSEM) was expanded by adding 6 classes for sea ice (Wang et al., 2017). FASTEM and TELSEM2 are implemented in the widely used fast radiative transfer model RTTOV. Although those emissivity models are frequently used for NWP, surface ice types are required as input for running the models. However, the 12 ice types used in the FASTEM model are difficult to identify and classify from satellite measurements. In addition, both approaches are less capable of describing temporal and spatial variations of the sea ice with the fixed coefficient sets and the monthly climatology atlas.

However, developing a sea ice emission model which is useful as an observation operator is not straight forward. So far the development of observation operators for sea ice have been limited to 6 GHz where scattering is not an issue (Burgard et al., 2020a and 2020b). While large scale sea ice models do compute the snow and ice thickness and temperature, which is important for the sea ice microwave emission, the detailed input, which is also important, to simulate sea ice microwave emission is usually not available: snow stratigraphy, snow and ice salinity profiles, snow grain sizes and ice inclusion sizes and distribution (Tonboe, 2010; Tonboe et al. 2011). Other studies have linked radiances at window channels with radiances at sounding channels (Tonboe et al., 2013). In this study we will build on earlier ESA (ESA sea ice Climate Change Initiative project development of model inversion procedures) and EU (development of forward models for both radars and radiometers in H2020 SPICES) investments and work towards the development of an observation operator for sea ice in the range of microwave frequencies from about 100 to 200 GHz and beyond using a state of the art emission model; SMRT (Snow Microwave Radiative Transfer; <https://www.smrt-model.science/>) and the output from a one dimensional sea ice model (Tonboe, 2010; Tonboe et al., 2022).

Here we will use optimal estimation in combination with the emission model SMRT to estimate simulated brightness temperatures and snow and ice parameters: snow depth, snow correlation length, and surface temperature. Optimal estimation is used here as a test-bed for evaluating the inversion of the emission model. It is expected that the inversion can be improved using coupled physical models (sea ice and atmospheric models) and data assimilation and that the results presented here are a worst case scenario.

In Figure 8 we show the correlation between selected physical snow and sea ice parameters and the

surface self-emission brightness temperature using a simulated dataset. The physical parameters are: Snow thick: snow depth, Ice thick: ice thickness, Surf temp: snow surface temperature, ACL growth: average snow auto-correlation length (a measure of snow grain size), ACL up: snow autocorrelation length of the surface layer, average density: average snow density, ice sal: ice salinity, snow thick up: thickness of the surface snow layer. The snow autocorrelation length has a direct influence on the brightness temperature variability while the thickness of the surface snow layer is unimportant.

Figure 8. The absolute correlation value between the physical snow and sea ice parameters and the simulated surface self-emission brightness temperature at frequencies between 6 and 183 GHz and at vertical and horizontal polarisation.

One future use of the surface emissivity model within the HARMONIE-AROME system could be to replace or complement the monthly surface emissivity atlases that are used in combination with the dynamical emissivity approach. This would be done by instead using surface emissivity estimates obtained with the problem derived here. It would as well be interesting to, over selected areas, compare use of surface emissivities using the emissivity model and the dynamical emissivity approach respectively. Towards the end of the project we aim to carry out such comparisons for selected cases.

3.1.5 Forecast impact experiments using dynamical emissivity method

Two sets of parallel experiments have been carried out over the Nordic MetCoOp domain (left panel of Fig. 1) to evaluate the effect of enhanced assimilation of low peaking channels as described in section 3.1.2 and 3.1.3 (handling over sea-ice). One of the parallel experiments was in the reference 3D-Var framework, which is currently used in operations at the Nordic weather services. The other experiment was carried out in the more advanced 4D-Var framework, applied in pre-operational mode in MetCoOp. The parallel experiments were performed for the one month

winter period February, 2021. This period was preceded by a two week period aimed for further spin-up of VARBC coefficients. A 3 h intermittent data assimilation cycle is applied. Forecasts up to 36 h are launched four times a day, from 00, 06 and 12 and 18 UTC. The two parallel experiments, carried out both for 3D-Var and 4D-Var, can be summarised as follows:

- CRL: reference experiment using conventional and various types of satellite-based observations.
- EXP: Like in CRL and in addition the surface sensitive channel 5 the surface sensitive channel 5 on AMSU-A and channel 5 on MHS (see Table 2 above) are used over land and sea-ice with a dynamic emissivities approach.

On a regional scale, the data coverage is not uniform in time and space over the domain of interest. As shown in Figure 9, the amount of available radiance data over land surfaces in the MetCoOp domain significantly depends on the time and the day. Over the period from 1 February 2021 to 20 February 2021 when the highest amount of AMSU-A and MHS were operational, one can note that 09 UTC and 18 UTC benefit from the best coverage, especially from the Metop instruments. There are no/few data available at 00 UTC and 03 UTC. The data amounts are based on MW usage without dynamical emissivity functionality introduced.

Figure 9. Amount of available AMSU-A and MHS observations over land.

The dynamical emissivity approach clearly allows more MW observations to enter the assimilation over land areas, in particular for low-peaking surface sensitive channels. This allows for a more efficient use of MW observations. This is illustrated in Figure 10, which shows the AMSU-A amount of used observations, accumulated over the one month experiment period.

Figure 10. Active observations per satellite (upper panels) and per AMSU-A channel ID (lower panels) for CTL (left) and LDYN (middle) and the difference between the two methods (right).

Observing the impact of the assimilation of low-peaking channels from AMSU-A and MHS instruments with the 3D-Var and 4D-Var assimilation approaches, we first put our attention on observation minus background (OmB) statistics. This impact assessment is carried out using the ratio of normalised differences in OmB, with an uncertainty estimate included. The estimate is derived from the standard deviations of the differences in OmB between low-peaking channels, with uncertainty estimates in Figure 11 for 3D-Var and in Figure 12 for 4D-Var. The idea is to verify the short range (1-3 h) forecasts against other observation types used within the data assimilation system, not modified between the experiments. We have picked observation types mainly sensitive to atmospheric temperature and moisture: radiosonde(TEMP)/aircraft(AIREP) temperatures, IASI water vapour sensitive channels and IASI long wave temperature sensitive channels. Theoretically, if the data within the error estimate does not touch the vertical line at 1, a 95% confidence level is ensured.

The analysis reveals that the introduction of low peaking channels results in a slightly improved agreement of the short-range forecasts with other observation types, although the results are insignificant, at the 95% significance level. The results are rather consistent between 3D-Var and 4D-Var experiments. However, a slightly larger positive impact on the wind field (not shown) can be observed in the 4D-Var experiment. This is likely due to the more advanced data-assimilation method, which also includes a flow dependency. Although the impact in terms of OmB statistics is not drastic, a potential for improved model performance by introduction of low-peaking channels using a dynamical emissivity approach is indicated, in particular for moisture sensitive IASI channels.

Figure 11. Normalised standard deviation statistics of the Observation minus Background for radiosonde and aircraft temperature, IASI water vapour and IASI long wave channels. Based on differences between EXP and CRL for the 3D-Var framework.

Figure 12. Normalised standard deviation statistics of the Observation minus Background for radiosonde and aircraft temperature, IASI water vapour and IASI long wave channels. Based on differences between EXP and CRL for the 4D-Var framework.

The effect of using low peaking channels on forecast quality at ranges up to 36 h is mainly seen in the form of a positive impact in terms of bias and standard deviation when verified against observations available within the domain. This is illustrated for two-metre relative humidity as function of forecast length for the 3D-Var parallel experiment in Figure 13 and for the 4D-Var parallel experiment in Figure 14. It can be seen that there is a clear positive impact of using low peaking channels both on two-metre relative humidity bias and standard deviation, both with 3D-Var and 4D-Var. Furthermore the improvement is demonstrated statistically significant, here illustrated in terms of root-mean square error (RMSE). A similar positive impact can as well be seen for lower atmospheric humidities, in particular in the 4D-Var framework. This positive impact on low level humidities as well brings an improvement in cloud-forecasts. In terms of temperature the scores are rather neutral for the lower atmosphere and even worse for the two-metre temperature in the 3D-Var framework.

Figure 13. Bias (left) and standard deviation (middle) of two-metre relative humidity forecasts as a function of forecast range and verified against all synoptical measurements within the domain. Red curve is for EXP and blue for CRL. Also shown (right) is difference in terms of RMSE between the two experiments and with 95% confidence level indicated by grey shaded area. values below 0 indicate better forecasts with EXP. Results are for the 3D-Var assimilation system.

Figure 14. Bias (left) and standard deviation (middle) of two-metre relative humidity forecasts as function of forecast range and verified against all synoptical measurements within the domain. Red curve is for EXP and blue for CRL. Also shown (right) is difference in terms of RMSE between the two experiments and with 95% confidence level indicated by grey shaded area. values below 0 indicate better forecasts with EXP. Results are for the 4D-Var assimilation system.

The scorecards (Figure 15) provide a comprehensive overview of the forecast impact on various variables. They show here EXP-CRL RMSE forecast differences and for various parameters for 3D-Var (left) and 4D-Var (right) framework and for various model parameters as function of forecast range. The scorecards include the following model parameters: Accumulated precipitation within 3, 6 and 12 h intervals (AccPcp3h, AccPcp6h, AccPcp12h), Cloud base and Cloud cover (Cbase, CC), ten-metre wind speed and direction (S10, D10), surface pressure and mean sea level pressure (Ps, Pmsl), two-metre temperature (T2m), two-metre dew point temperature (Td2m), two metre specific humidity (Q2), two metre relative humidity (RH2m). In addition, for upper-air variables geopotential height (Z), temperature (T), Relative humidity (RH), specific humidity (Q) and wind speed (S) at the vertical levels of 850, 500 and 150 hPa. For surface parameters, the verification is done against a large amount of synoptical observations. For upper-air parameters verification is done against radiosonde observations within the domain (much fewer than surface observations).

A positive and often significant influence on cloud base height (Cbase), total cloud cover (Ctot), dew point temperature (Td2m), 2m humidity (Q2m), and relative humidity (RH2m) is seen, with significantly improved RMSE present for the first 24 hours, both for 3D-Var and 4D-Var. However, the impact on other variables like two-metre temperature (T2m), mean sea level pressure (Pmsl), 10m wind speed (S10m) and ten-metre wind direction tended to be slightly negative for 3D-Var, though primarily insignificant. For those variables the more advanced 4D-Var assimilation system brought an improvement to the enhancement obtained through use of low-peaking channels. For upper-air variables the impact is rather mixed and insignificant. The slight (insignificant) improvement brought by the use of low-peaking channels to lower level relative humidity forecasts, is visible in the scorecards.

Figure 15. Scorecards for EXP-CRL RMSE forecast differences and for various parameters for 3D-Var (left) and 4D-Var (right) framework.

The overall conclusion from the data assimilation and forecast experiment focusing on Nordic winter conditions is a small but overall positive impact of the enhancements using a dynamical emissivity approach for enhanced use of low-peaking channels from MW instruments. We demonstrated increased use of observations and brought small improvements to our reference data assimilation system using 3D-Var. The future improvement in terms of forecast impact by using more advanced data assimilation methods was indicated by the slightly larger positive impact in the more advanced 4D-Var system than in the operational 3D-Var.

Taking the 3D-Var run with use of low-peaking channels applying the dynamical emissivity approach with the specular emissivity approach as reference, an additional run has been carried out for February 2021. The additional run is exactly the same as the reference run, except for that a Lambertian reflectivity assumption has been applied. A similar parallel experiment is currently being carried out also with 4D-Var.

Figure 16 shows, for the 3D-Var parallel experiment, histograms of observation minus background departures for all MHS and AMSU-A channel 5 observations assimilated during the one-month winter period and over surfaces identified as covered by sea-ice and snow. These are the lowest peaking channels used for AMSU-A and MHS and the ones most influenced by the reflection assumption. It can be seen that encouragingly MHS histograms are more centred around zero when applying the Lambertian reflectivity assumption. In addition, it seems that more AMSU-A observations are used over snow surfaces.

Figure 16. Histograms of first-guess departures (observation minus model equivalent) of MHS (upper) and AMSU-A (lower) channel 5 brightness temperatures for all February 2023 data assimilation cycles and with specular (red) and Lambertian (blue) emissivity assumption. Left column is for areas identified as covered by snow and left for areas identified as covered by sea-ice.

Limitations of the currently investigated approach is however that the Lambertian reflection assumption is not only applied over sea-ice and snow surfaces, but over all surfaces. In addition there is currently no technical possibility to combine so that one for example assumes 50% specular and 50% Lambertian reflection, within the modelling framework. Results with current assumptions are illustrated in Figure 17 for forecasts of surface temperature and moisture and in Figure 18 for upper-air vertical profiles of temperature and moisture and for the entire modelling area. Clearly the reflection assumption has a large effect on the forecast verification scores. For surface scores, there is a clear degradation, in particular in terms of an increased bias when introducing the Lambertian reflectivity assumption. For the lower atmosphere, scores are rather neutral or positive for humidity, whereas there is a positive impact from the Lambertian reflectivity on lower tropospheric temperatures.

Figure 17. Standard deviation and bias of two-metre temperature (left) and two-metre specific humidity (right) forecasts as function of forecast range (h). The scores are for verification against all surface observations within the model domain and for February 2021. Red curves are for Specular assumption and green curves for Lambertian.

Figure 18. Vertical profiles of standard deviation and bias temperature (left) and specific humidity (right) forecasts. Scores are averaged over forecast ranges from +6 to +24 hours. The scores are for verification against all radiosonde observations within the model domain and for February 2021. Red curves are for Specular assumption and green curves for Lambertian.

Based on the mixed results so far, the Lambertian reflectivity assumptions will not yet be included as default in the HARMONIE-AROME AWS modelling system. The results from 4D-Var will reveal the importance of a more advanced data assimilation system and limiting effects of the assimilation system, such as background error statistics, that are somewhat alleviated with 4D-VAR. Furthermore we will exploit if more flexible combinations of Specular and Lambertian reflectivity assumptions can be implemented into the modelling system within the time-frame of the project.

3.2. Handling of observation and model scale differences by using a footprint operator

A microwave radiance footprint operator was developed for cross-track scanning instruments like AWS and tested with AMSU-A and MHS satellite radiances. The source code implementation has been done in cy43h2. The modifications have been merged with the AWS branch (including

contributions from other work packages).

3.2.1. The concept of satellite footprint representation

The satellite field-of-view (FOV) is not appropriately represented in high-resolution DA systems by the existing observation operator, which increases the representation error in satellite data assimilation. The representation error (Janjić et al., 2017) by definition is an error component which might come from the unresolved scales and processes of the high-resolution observations.

Although, the opposite scale mismatch often occurs when unobserved scales and processes of the high-resolution model are the source of this type of error (see Marseille and Stoffelen, 2017; Mile et al., 2021). A footprint observation operator aims to reduce the error related to spatial representation error by aggregating the small-scale model quantities in the DA. Footprint operators have been implemented in certain geoscientific applications like in regional ice analysis system of Environment Climate Change Canada (Buehner et al., 2013; Carrieres et al., 2017) or have been studied in the scatterometer and Aeolus data assimilation (Mile et al., 2021, 2022). In radiance data assimilation, the relevance of the satellite footprint representation has also been recognised.

Kleespies (2009) showed that averaged model surface quantities over the satellite footprint of the microwave radiances are important when the surface parameters vary substantially. Probably for the first time, Duffourg et al. (2010) studied a radiance footprint operator of infrared radiances for a convective-scale DA system and over the Mediterranean domain. In this project, the footprint representation of microwave satellite radiances from AMSU-A and MHS sensors is studied in order to prepare the HARMONIE-AROME system for a more optimal use of AWS radiances in the future.

The footprint by definition is the instantaneous intersection of the antenna pattern at half the maximum power level i.e., the 3dB contour, that is the Instantaneous FOV (IFOV). The major and minor axes are defined by the maximum and minimum distances respectively between any two points on the footprint contour. The direction of the minor axis is orthogonal to the major axis. The obvious way to eliminate the representation error of satellite radiances is to design a *proper* footprint observation operator. Proper here means that the entire area of the satellite footprint ellipse is considered in the computation of model-equivalent radiances. In this project, an IFOV footprint operator was explored and studied with AMSU-A and MHS radiances. However, it's worth mentioning that the footprint is just the instantaneous intersection of the antenna pattern as it was mentioned earlier. The effective field-of-view (EFOV) i.e, the area swept by the antenna beam is generally 2.5 times larger than the IFOV which is the real observed area by the sensor.. In the next phase of the footprint operator developments, the EFOV will be considered and the prototype footprint operator can be extended for EFOV representation.

In the case of existing cross-track scanning sensors (e.g., AMSU-A, MHS,ATMS) , the IFOV area at nadir forms a perfectly circular footprint and when the sensor looks towards the edge of the swath, the footprint area elongates notably in the cross-track while slightly in the along-track directions as well. For AWS, the IFOV sizes and the orientation of footprint ellipses differ from heritage scanners bringing additional complexity in the footprint representation (see Albers et al., 2023). The footprint ellipses of radiance instruments can be horizontally described and defined by their minor and major axes relative to the nadir viewing angle of the satellite. The viewing angle of the pixel centre and the vertices of a given IFOV ellipse can be expressed as

$$\lambda_s = \frac{\delta_{step}}{2} + (p-1) * \delta_{step} - \epsilon \quad (6) \quad \lambda_e = \frac{\delta_{step}}{2} + (p-1) * \delta_{step} + \epsilon \quad (7) \quad \lambda = \frac{\delta_{step}}{2} + (p-1) * \delta_{step}, \quad (8)$$

where the δ_{step} and ϵ stand for the sampling angular interval (i.e., centre to centre IFOV step angle) and the half of the IFOV width respectively. p means the pixel number, furthermore, λ , λ_s , λ_e stand for the viewing or scanning angle of the pixel centre and the two cross-track (i.e., start and end) vertices of the IFOV ellipse respectively. These λ viewing angles can be converted in order to obtain the scanning angle (hereafter β) on the Earth's frame as the following

$$\beta_s = \arcsin\left(\left(\frac{R+H}{R}\right) * \sin(\lambda_s)\right) - \lambda_s, \quad (9)$$

$$\beta_e = \arcsin\left(\left(\frac{R+H}{R}\right) * \sin(\lambda_e)\right) - \lambda_e, \quad (10)$$

$$\beta = \arcsin\left(\left(\frac{R+H}{R}\right) * \sin(\lambda)\right) - \lambda, \quad (11)$$

where the R is the Earth's radius and H is the altitude of the satellite at a given geographical location. The length of the major axis of an IFOV ellipse on the Earth's surface, therefore, can be expressed as follows

$$d_{\text{major}} = (\beta_e - \beta_s) * R, \quad (12)$$

and the satellite's slant-path can also be expressed using the law of sines to compute the minor axis of the IFOV ellipse as follows

$$d_{\text{path}} = \frac{R * \sin(\beta)}{\sin(\lambda)} \quad (13) \quad d_{\text{minor}} = d_{\text{path}} * 2\epsilon. \quad (14)$$

Using d_{major} and d_{minor} , the actual size of the IFOV can be calculated and used for the footprint operator. The spatial sampling of the footprint operator points (hereafter FOPs) should reflect the horizontal resolution of the applied NWP model taking into account the characteristics of the ground-projected IFOV. Examples of selected FOPs are shown on Figure 19 for a given AMSU-A scanline and MHS scanlines near the Svalbard archipelago.

Figure 19. The FOPs for AMSU-A (red) and MHS IFOVs (blue) on Metop-C satellite for different scanlines around the nadir. Sample taken from measurement on 20 March, 2020, 08:27 UTC.

3.2.2. The basic features of the implementation inside the variational scheme of the HARMONIE-AROME model

In the variational assimilation framework, the observation operator does the computation of the model equivalent of the assimilated observation. The implementation of the radiance footprint operator can follow different coding strategies using the features or elements of the default radiance observation operator. In this project, the footprint representation in observation space is chosen performing the aggregation after the RTTOV simulation. Computationally, it means a more expensive approach than for instance to average model quantities before the RTTOV calls. However, this allows us to take into account the non-linearity in the RTTOV simulation resulting in more accurate final model-equivalents for data assimilation. It uses interpolated model information to represent the satellite IFOV, what we called FOPs. In the variational assimilation scheme, a nonlinear observation operator can be used, but the minimization requires a tangent-linear and an adjoint operator as well. The footprint operator in our case is built around the default radiance observation operator meaning that the adjoint footprint operator is basically the transpose of the linear averaging operator. In order to verify the correctness of the implemented adjoint operator, the adjoint identity test was produced and showed relative error comparable with machine precision (not shown).

One technical challenge for this radiance observation operator is that the default system is based on the information stored in the observation database (ODB) for a single geolocation and not designed to handle for instance emissivity of the additional FOPs (i.e., many more geolocation for a single observation). This is particularly challenging for retrieved emissivity which cannot be stored in the default ODB. Therefore, the ODB was extended in order to store and access additional emissivity information specifically for the footprint operator. In Figure 20, the retrieved dynamical emissivity

values are shown for each FOP for AMSU-A pixels before and after the data screening procedure (blacklisting, quality control, data thinning, etc).

Figure 20. Maps of emissivity retrievals using all available AMSU-A 54.40 GHz channel (a) and active (b) observations from NOAA-19 satellite, 20 March, 2020, at 9:00 UTC using the radiance footprint operator.

The sub-footprint variability in the simulated brightness temperatures indicates areas where the use of the footprint operator is potentially more beneficial. On Figure 21a and 21b, the variability inside each AMSU-A footprint is shown for data from the 23.8 and 54.94 GHz channels respectively. The colour scales on Figure 21a and 21b are different and it allows to show only those IFOVs where the standard deviation is the highest. The high variability in the observation equivalent is associated with the impact of mixed surfaces inside the IFOV. High-peaking channels of AMSU-A are less or not sensitive to the surface, therefore, sub-footprint variability is not related to mixed surface conditions. On Figure 21b, the variability in model equivalents of AMSU-A radiances considering the 54.94 GHz channel (channel 7) is plotted and the highest variability is obtained close to the edge of the satellite scan. It might be explained by the fact that IFOV sizes are larger near the edges of the swath and the corresponding resolution gap is also larger between the model and the observation.

Figure 21. The variability in the simulated brightness temperatures inside the footprint of AMSU-A window channel (23.8 GHz) (a) and high-peaking channel (54.94 GHz) (b) from the NOAA-19 satellite on 20 March 2020 at 9 UTC.

3.2.3. Departure-based diagnostics and observing system experiments with AMSU-A footprint operator

Observing system experiments (OSEs) were carried out with 3D-Var and 4D-Var running the MetCoOp configuration of the HARMONIE-AROME. First, observation minus background forecast (OMB) departures are examined comparing the statistics of AMSU-A data assimilation with the default and the radiance footprint observation operators. The performance of both observation operators is assessed over a two-month period (between 1 January and 28 February, 2021). The AMSU-A observations from Metop-B, Metop-C, NOAA-18, and NOAA-19 satellites are used whitelisting IFOVs near the edges of the swath. Apart from the applied observation operators, the default assimilation settings, namely, the predefined observation and background errors, thinning distances, and the quality control procedure were the same in both assimilation experiments.

In Figure 22a and 22b, the standard deviation of OMB departures for AMSU-A 53.59 and 54.94 GHz channels are shown as a function of satellite scanning positions. By the use of the radiance footprint operator, the reduction in OMB statistics for both channels is apparent and somewhat larger for low-peaking channel (Figure 22a) which is expected. For channel 7 (54.94 GHz), the reduction is more pronounced for pixels near the edge of the swath which is consistent with the highest variability indicated on Figure 21b.

Figure 22. The standard deviation of observation minus MetCoOp forecasts of AMSU-A 53.59 (a) and 54.94 GHz (b) channels as a function of satellite scanning position. The black line stands for the default and the red line is for the footprint operator respectively.

OSEs were carried out with conventional (including atmospheric motion vectors and scatterometer ocean wind data) and AMSU-A observations with the operational 3D-Var MetCoOp HARMONIE-AROME model configuration in order to assess the added value of the AMSU-A radiance footprint operator. Two experiments were conducted: default radiance observation operator including the development of WP2.1.2, denoted “EXPDEF” and footprint observation operator including the development of WP2.1.2 denoted “EXPFOP”. The forecasts from these experiments are verified against radiosondes and the corresponding errors denoted “RMSEDEF” and “RMSEFOP” respectively. The normalised difference of EXPFOP and EXPDEF is obtained from $(RMSEFOP - RMSEDEF) / RMSEFOP$, with negative/positive values denoting positive/negative impact of the footprint relative to the default observation operator.

In conclusion, the overall impact of the radiance footprint operator is neutral to positive and significant positive impact was obtained in particular for short term (up to 12 hours) temperature forecasts initialised from 06 UTC analyses (see on Figure 23 below).

Figure 23. Normalised root mean square error (RMSE) difference (90% confidence) (Footprint operator vs. Default operator in 3D-Var) verification using radiosonde data: MetCoOp 06 UTC temperature +00-hr (a), +06-hr (b), +12-hr ©, +18-hr (d), and +24-hr (e) forecasts; Verification period: 1st to 28th of Feb., 2021.

Beside the 3D-Var OSEs, time-consistent 4D-Var experiments were conducted as well. It's worth noting that the minimization of HARMONIE-AROME 4D-Var is performed on a coarser-resolution model grid which makes the resolution gap and the related representation error in radiance data assimilation smaller than with 3D-Var. It also requires different sampling in the high-resolution trajectory runs and in the coarse-resolution minimization loops. On Figure 24, the sampling resolution for a single AMSU-A scanline and the retrieved dynamical emissivity values for all footprint operator points are shown.

Figure 24. Footprint operator sampling in high-resolution (2.5 km) screening trajectory for a single scanline near nadir (a), in coarse-resolution (7.5 km) minimization loop 1 (b), and in coarse-resolution (15 km) minimization loop 2 (c). Retrieved emissivity for all footprint operator points in high-resolution trajectory (d), 7.5 km minimization (e), and 15 km minimization runs.

Using the same verification metrics and the normalised RMSE differences, the performance of default and footprint observation operators was compared with the 4D-Var scheme. In conclusion, the impact of AMSU-A footprint representation is neutral. In 3D-Var, positive impact was obtained for temperature forecasts initialised at 06 UTC, however, in 4D-Var, the impact is also neutral for this particular MetCoOp forecast parameter (see Figure 25 below).

Figure 25. Normalised root mean square error (RMSE) difference (90% confidence) (Footprint operator vs. Default operator in 4D-Var) verification using radiosonde data: MetCoOp 06 UTC temperature +00-hr (a), +06-hr (b), +12-hr (c), +18-hr (d), and +24-hr (e) forecasts; Verification period: 1st to 28th of Feb., 2021.

3.3. Towards use of satellite MW radiances from all-sky conditions

3.3.1 Introduction

Work towards future all-sky operational use of satellite radiances involves several aspects. The RTTOV-SCATT (the scattering solver of RTTOV; Geer et al., 2021) observation operator, to be used in the full-scale all-sky HARMONIE-AROME satellite radiance data assimilation, includes interfaces to model physics and also some parameterizations in the form of assumed particle size distributions. Since HARMONIE-AROME shares a common modelling base with ECMWF IFS, it is of importance to exploit adaptations needed for use of RTTOV-SCATT together with HARMONIE-AROME model physics. These studies include comparison of HARMONIE-AROME cloud-microphysics with ground based measurements, exploiting importance of snow Particle Size Distribution (PSD) and particle habit assumptions, and full scale HARMONIE-AROME studies.

3.3.2 Evaluation of HARMONIE-AROME cloud microphysics against in-situ measurements

The representation of cloud physics in HARMONIE-AROME concerns the presence of water in all three phases (vapour, liquid, solid) and is separated into schemes for warm (liquid) cloud microphysics and cold (solid) cloud microphysics. These schemes provide prognostic equations for 6 or 7 water categories or ‘species’: water vapour; two species for warm clouds; and 3 or 4 species for cold clouds. The warm cloud microphysics schemes use one or two moment schemes to prognose the mixing ratios (and number concentrations in two moment schemes) of cloud liquid water, and precipitation (which may correspond to rain or drizzle depending on cloud type).

Atmospheric ice particles occur in an extremely wide variety of shapes, sizes and densities. Hence, in an attempt to parametrize this complexity, the cold cloud microphysics schemes for most numerical weather prediction models comprise three or four species: ice, snow, graupel and hail (graupel may be combined with hail in some microphysical schemes), for which each may have a

prognostic equation for their mixing ratio and possibly their number concentration (two-moment schemes). The distinction between these four species is model (and scheme) -dependent, meaning that, for example, the ice and snow categories in HARMONIE-AROME may not correspond directly to the categories with the same name in the ECMWF IFS model. For HARMONIE-AROME, *ice* refers to ‘pristine ice’ arising from heterogeneous nucleation processes, *snow* refers to crystal aggregates or lightly rimed large ice crystals, *graupel* refers to heavily rimed ice crystals (still relatively low density), and *hail* is frozen drops (high density ice).

In HARMONIE-AROME, mixed-phase clouds are considered in terms of both cold and warm microphysics, where supercooled cloud liquid water is represented using the same formulations as for warm cloud liquid water.

Ground-based cloud observations with high spatial and temporal resolution can be obtained from the combination of active and passive instruments given in Fig. 26a: a cloud radar, lidar or ceilometer (low-powered lidar), and a (usually multi-frequency) microwave radiometer (Illingworth et al. 2007). However, this ground-based active profiling of clouds is usually limited to vertical observations, which are very sparse. At the time of this study there were three ground-based cloud profiling stations (Fig. 26b) operating within the MetCoOp domain shown in Fig. 1: the Meteorological Observatory Lindenberg in Germany operated by DWD; the Norunda research station (cloud profiling instruments operated by SMHI and ICOS Sweden); and SMEAR II (Station for Measuring Ecosystem-Atmosphere Relations) operated by the University of Helsinki at Hyytiälä, Finland.

Figure 26. a) Ground-based cloud remote sensing instruments, clockwise from top left: cloud radar, ceilometer, multi-channel microwave radiometer. b) Ground-based measurement locations within the MetCoOp domain: Lindenberg, Germany; Norunda, Sweden; Hyytiälä, Finland.

For warm microphysics, the observed separation between liquid cloud and precipitation (rain or drizzle) is similar to how it is represented in models, with individual retrievals for liquid cloud microphysics and for warm precipitation. However, for cold microphysics, the observations do not follow the model representation of separate distinct categories; the instruments observe a continuum of ice particles ranging from pristine crystals, through aggregates to rimed structures, with microphysical retrievals typically encompassing all of these within one ice category (or specie). Hence, care must be taken when comparing models and observations to ensure that like is being compared with like.

Since clouds can vary rapidly in both space and time, and observations are profiles from sparse stations, the evaluation process makes use of advective averaging to transform from the observation domain (time) to the model domain (space), where observation time is translated to the time taken for a model to advect a model grid box over the station (Illingworth et al. 2007). The evaluation process used here identifies whether the model has clouds in the right place at the right time, assessed by comparing the vertical profile of the cloud fraction variable, and whether they have the correct bulk microphysics in terms of the water content (note that only the solid water content is assessed in this report, since of main importance for assimilation of MW radiances). In addition, good evaluation statistics for the entire vertical profile require the aggregation of long-term datasets covering several months at least.

Figure 27 shows the cloud cover and ice water content of HARMONIE-AROME short range forecasts in comparison to observations at the Norunda cloud-profiling station. The main conclusion is that, overall, better agreement with observations is obtained if the model parameters snow and graupel are included in the model cloud fraction and ice water content derivations. However, amounts of ice water content above a given threshold are forecasted too often by the model.

Figure 27. Evaluation of MetCoop operational model ($t+3$ hours) using cloud profiling data from Norunda, Sweden; left panel) mean cloud fraction; centre panel) mean ice water content; right panel) frequency of occurrence of ice water content above a particular threshold. Cloud fraction evaluation used the equivalent of 215.5 days of data, ice water content evaluation used the equivalent of 191.6 days of data. Observation (blue), full model equivalents (grey), model equivalents with undetectable ice² removed without graupel and snow included (solid red) and model equivalents with undetectable ice removed with graupel and snow included (dashed red).

The left panel of Figure 28 shows the comparison of observed and modelled cloud fraction over the Norunda cloud profiling station in Sweden. For cold clouds in HARMONIE-AROME, only the ice category has a corresponding cloud fraction, hence the major underestimate by the model compared to observations; much better agreement between observations and model is seen once the model snow and graupel categories are also considered to contribute to cloud fraction. This is also the case for the mean ice water content (Figure 27 centre panel), which compares quite well at all levels once snow and graupel water content contributions are included. The snow and graupel water contents are significantly higher than the ice water content at all levels except close to the tropopause. Of interest here is that the snow and graupel water contents for HARMONIE-AROME are quite similar in magnitude (not shown) which is not necessarily the case for other model microphysical schemes (e.g. for the ECMWF IFS model).

² Modelled ice clouds that are too tenuous to be detected are identified and removed from the analysis using the known sensitivity of the cloud radar, which varies with range. The procedure parametrizes the expected horizontal variability of ice water content within a model grid box (Hogan and Illingworth, 2003) and also accounts for any extra attenuation of the radar signal due to gas, liquid water, and rain.

Figure 28. Evaluation of MetCoop operational model ($t+3$ hours) ice water content, mean amount when present above a specific threshold, using cloud profiling data from left) Norunda, Sweden; centre panel) Hyytiälä, Finland; right panel) Lindenberg, Germany. All ice water content evaluation used the equivalent of more than 140 days of data. Observation (blue), full model equivalents (grey), model equivalents with undetectable ice removed without graupel and snow included (solid red) and model equivalents with undetectable ice removed with graupel and snow included (dashed red).

It is possible to get the correct mean amount of ice water content for the wrong reason, for example when there are compensating errors, and additional metrics to investigate this include the *frequency of occurrence*, which seeks to understand how often clouds occur, and *amount when present*, which tests the water content of the clouds that are present. These two metrics are calculated with respect to specific threshold amounts of water content, here we use a low threshold ice water content. Above Norunda, the model displays a frequency of occurrence of ice that is too high throughout most of the vertical profile once snow and graupel water contents are included (Figure 27 right panel). High clouds above about eight km in altitude in the model display too high a frequency of occurrence even if snow and graupel are not included. At the same time, there is not enough cold water content in mid-level clouds between 2 and 7 km in altitude (Figure 28 left panel). The cold water content in high level clouds above 7 km agree well with observations, but the mean cold water content is overestimated because these clouds are forecast too frequently.

Over Hyytiälä, which is at a similar latitude to Norunda, the cold water content in mid-level cloud is also underestimated, while there is an overestimate in the mid-level cloud cold water content at Lindenberg further south (Figure 28). Figure 28 also shows that the model cold water content is too high at low levels at all locations. A possible explanation for this robust feature is that the model produces too much cold water content in the graupel category, with faster falling graupel having less time to sublime as it falls compared to low density aggregates if the water content was classed in the snow category. Any incorrect partitioning of cold water contents across the cold categories has implications when assimilating high water content values within the HARMONIE-AROME model.

3.3.3 Off-line simulation experiments

The PSD used for parametrization of atmospheric ice in the RTTOV-SCATT observation operator differs from the representation in the HARMONIE-AROME model. HARMONIE-AROME uses versions of the modified gamma distribution (MGD) as PSD for three categories of atmospheric ice: pristine ice, ice aggregates (snow) and graupel/hail. The standard parametrization of atmospheric snow and graupel in RTTOV-SCATT (Geer et al., 2021) is defined by a PSD tuned by Field et al., 2007 (F07) where a two-moment rescaling procedure was used to fit the PSD to observations of tropical ice clouds. One main difference between F07 and the versions of MGD used for snow and graupel in HARMONIE-AROME is that the former has a temperature dependence while this is not the case for the HARMONIE-AROME version of MGD as is demonstrated in the left panel of Figure 29. The difference is most significant for smaller particles that are not relevant for MW

observations. Figure 2 in Ekelund et al., 2020 shows the sensitivity to different particle sizes for high frequency MW radiation. For F07 it is seen that the sensitivity for particles below about 0.1 mm is very low.

In addition to a PSD, radiative transfer simulations require a particle habit with precalculated single scattering properties to determine the extinction in each atmospheric layer. Particle habits from Atmospheric Radiative Transfer Simulator (ARTS) single scattering database (Eriksson et al., 2018) are used in RTTOV-SCATT and the habits considered in this study are seen in Figure 30. The updated version of RTTOV-SCATT, here referred to as RTTOV v13, uses the Large Plate Aggregate (LPA) and the older versions, currently used at SMHI, RTTOV v11/v12 uses Liu Sector Snowflake (LSS).

Figure 29. Particle size distributions (PSD) for different snow models with typical amounts of snow water content (SWC) of 0.1 g/m^3 . The left figure is for the same habit (LPA) but different PSDs (F07 and MGD) where the temperature dependence of F07 is shown for a typical range of temperatures. The right figure is for the same PSD (MGD) but different habits (IconSnow, LPA and ESA).

Both HARMONIE-AROME and RTTOV-SCATT assume a power law relation, $m = aD_{max}^b$ between particle mass (m) and maximum diameter (D_{max}) to derive the PSDs. For

HARMONIE-AROME the scaling constant, a , and exponent, b , are found in (Meso-NH documentation) while for RTTOV-SCATT they are associated with the particle habit of consideration and can be found in Eriksson et al., 2018. There is no perfect match for the a and b parameters of the particle habits in the ARTS database to the ones used in HARMONIE-AROME and thus the HARMONIE-AROME PSD will inevitably differ slightly when implementing it in a radiative transfer simulation context if mass is to be conserved. The particle habit with a and b parameters closest to the ones used in HARMONIE-AROME for snow is the IconSnow seen in Figure 28, and Figure 29 shows the deviation between MGD implemented with the IconSnow habit and the HARMONIE-AROME MGD.

Figure 30. Particle habits from ARTS single scattering database (Eriksson et al., ESSD, 2018) used in the different snow models seen in Table 4.

To investigate the sensitivity of the choice of particle model i.e., the choice of PSD and particle habit, a simulation experiment using the reference model ARTS (Atmospheric Radiative Transfer Simulator) was performed. Satellite radiances in the MW regime were simulated using ARTS for different particle models and compared to real observations. The numerical atmospheric states for the simulations were defined from HARMONIE-AROME model data including ice water content (IWC) and temperature needed to calculate the PSDs. This study looked at observations from a conical scanner, GPM Microwave Imager (GMI), that have been used extensively in previous simulations with ARTS. This instrument was chosen due to its small footprint size and fixed incidence angle. Observations from the high frequency channels, 166 GHz (ch 10), 183±3 GHz (ch 12) and 183±7 GHz (ch 13), of GMI were simulated in two different geographical regions, Southeastern Sweden (SES) and Bothnian Bay (BB), seen in Figure 31. The seven most cloudy scenes were selected for each region during the period March to August in 2021. To determine whether the scene was cloudy, a cloud fraction was defined as

$$\text{Cloud fraction} = \frac{\text{number of observations with } Tb_{ch13} < Tb_{limit}}{\text{total number of observations}}$$

where “number of observations” refers to the number of observations within the considered region and Tb_{ch13} is the brightness temperature for channel 13. The limit Tb_{limit} was chosen to be 160 K

and only scenes with a cloud fraction > 0.05 was selected. The selected observations were then matched to the closest time-step in HARMONIE-AROME and a numerical atmospheric state was generated from HARMONIE-AROME data. Only scenes with observations within ±15 min of a HARMONIE-AROME time-step were included and the numerical scene was generated for an area roughly 2 degrees larger than the area where observations were simulated (see Figure 30) to accommodate the slant path from ground position to the sensor.

Figure 31. The Coloured area shows the geographical regions where numerical scenes from HA model data were generated using ARTSceneGenerator (ASG) and the dashed lines mark where GMI observations were simulated using ARTS.

Microwave radiation is more sensitive to snow compared to ice and to keep the number of varying parameters down this study started to consider different particle models for the snow category of atmospheric ice. Five different snow models were tested, summarised in Table 4. The two snow models used in RTTOV v11/v12 and v13 respectively and three models with the HARMONIE-AROME MGD but different particle habits. Figure 28 shows the PSD for the different snow models for a typical amount of SWC.

Table 4: Snow particle models consisting of a particle size distribution (PSD) and a particle habit. The particle habits (and corresponding a and b parameters) are taken from ARTS single scattering database (Eriksson et al., 2018).

Snow Model	Particle Size Distribution	Particle Habit
HA IconSnow	Modified Gamma Distribution (MGD)	Icon Snow
HA LPA	Modified Gamma Distribution (MGD)	Large Plate Aggregate (LPA)
HA ESA	Modified Gamma Distribution (MGD)	Evans Snow Aggregate (ESA)
RTTOV v11/v12	Field et al., 2007	Liu Sector Snowflake (LSS)
RTTOV v13	Field et al., 2007	Large Plate Aggregate (LPA)

Figure 32 shows the distribution of brightness temperatures (T_b) for all observations and simulations in all seven scenes for the SES and BB region separately. The snow models HA LPA and RTTOV v11/v12 are seen to follow each other very closely for all channels and in both regions. They are also seen to show more impact of snow scattering than the other models, thus capturing more of the low brightness temperatures seen in the observations. RTTOV v13 shows slightly less scattering but is also fairly similar to HA LPA and RTTOV v11/v12. The model that resembles the HARMONIE-AROME parametrization the most, HA IconSnow, shows even less scattering and thus also agrees less with the observations. Least scattering is seen for HA ESA in Figure 31 and it is noted that the performance of the HARMONIE-AROME PSD varies significantly depending on particle habit.

From the results shown in this study, one can conclude that there is no specific reason to mimic the HARMONIE-AROME snow model for radiative transfer simulations. The HA IconSnow model, with a and b parameters closest to the parameter values used in HARMONIE-AROME, agreed less with observations than the standard model used in RTTOV-SCATT. Using the HARMONIE-AROME PSD together with the LPA habit improved the performance compared to using IconSnow, suggesting that a tuning of the HARMONIE-AROME PSD is needed where different particle habits are tested. Considering that the RTTOV-SCATT models seem to work well and are well tested in previous studies, the use of the RTTOV-SCATT model is preferable to such tuning of the HARMONIE-AROME model.

Figure 32. Brightness temperature (T_b) distributions for 7 scenes in the SES (left) and BB (right) regions for GMI channels 10, 13 and 12.

3.3.4 Full-scale 3D-modelling studies

Implementation of the ECMWF IFS all-sky (Geer et al. 2018) approach has started in the HARMONIE-AROME data assimilation system. The work is started in model version cy46 and with MHS observations. HARMONIE-AROME cy46 is a newer version of the system, than the operationally used cy43. In the all-sky approach the radiance observation operator RTTOV is replaced by RTTOV-SCATT, which provides the model counterpart of the radiance observations in clear, cloudy and rainy conditions. Some first results have been obtained but substantial further work is needed before all-sky can be considered for operational use.

After activating the all-sky cy46 data assimilation over land we also introduced TELSEM2 emissivity maps in the HARMONIE-AROME data assimilation system. Following the comparison of HARMONIE-AROME forecasts with observations outlined in 3.3.2 we introduced an adaption of the all-sky functionality to the HARMONIE-AROME modelling system. It was clearly illustrated in the observational study that it has an effect to also include graupel and snow in the total ice water content calculated from HARMONIE-AROME background states. If doing so, HARMONIE-AROME timely averaged ice water content compares quite well at all levels, with observations. Since graupel is not a model variable in the ECMWF model microphysics parameterization scheme this quantity was not present in the original ECMWF interface to RTTOV-SCATT, but was included as a HARMONIE-AROME adaptation in the interface of RTTOV-SCATT to HARMONIE-AROME. The inclusion of graupel had an effect on the model equivalents of the all-sky brightness temperatures, but further in-depth studies are planned, when the full data assimilation runs are carried out. On the other hand, based on findings of off-line model simulations in 3.3.3, we have chosen to in the 3D-modelling framework use the RTTOV scatt default snow PDS and particle habit assumptions, rather than doing further HARMONIE-AROME adaptations.

Recent all-sky work has been concerned with introducing into HARMONIE-AROME the ECMWF functionality to remove observations very close to each other, so called thinning, prior to the data assimilation. The reasons are to reduce data volumes and to avoid effects of spatial observation error correlations, presently not represented in the data assimilation system. As a starting point we applied an all-sky thinning distance roughly corresponding to the one currently applied for clear-sky radiances in HARMONIE-AROME. Figure 33 below shows, for one particular date a comparison between all-sky and clear-sky MHS channel 3 and 4 after thinning and remaining data in data assimilation.

Figure 33. Data usage in minimization for MHS clear-sky (left) and all-sky (right) Metop-C and channel 4 after thinning the observations for 2nd september 2019 at 09:00 UTC

The blacklisting, including identification of poor quality channels and instruments, and surface affected channels etc, in all-sky is done similarly to the clear-sky approach. There is ongoing work to account for observation biases through VARBC. Figure 34 below shows the brightness temperature distribution from passive assimilation (observation and model equivalent comparison without data assimilation) of MHS channels 3 and 4 for all-sky conditions. With passive runs and selecting the observations that pass quality-control the distributions show the differences between model first-guess and observations from the passive runs. Upper-panel is for density as function of brightness temperature for model equivalents against observations while lower-panel shows the logarithm of the distribution as function of brightness temperature for model equivalents and observations. We see that with an all-sky approach a larger amount of low brightness temperature model equivalents are represented as compared to clear-sky. Clearly the all-sky model equivalents overestimates these low brightness temperatures at the lower part of the spectrum. This will be further investigated and the effect of VARBC evaluated.

Figure 34. distribution of all-sky model equivalents (blue), clear-sky model equivalents (green) and all (all-sky) observations (red) for MHS channels 3 and 4. Upper panel non-logarithmic distributions and lower panel with logarithmic distributions. From 1-10 September, 2019.

To evaluate the quality of all-sky brightness temperatures from HARMONIE-AROME a first 10 day period parallel data assimilation experiment with active all-sky MHS assimilation has been carried out. In this experiment also the lower peaking MHS channel 5 was activated, both over land and sea, but without use of the dynamical emissivity approach described in section 3.1.2 (the dynamical emissivity approach developments we focused on the clear-sky radiances that will be used in operations by the time of launch of AWS). As shown in Figure 35 mean observation minus analysis biases and departures are smaller than the bias and standard deviation of mean observation minus background departures. This demonstrates a proper general functionality of the MHS all-sky

assimilation. Note also, in agreement with discussions in 3.1.1 a large bias in MHS channel 5 departures. A future enhancement to be taken onboard by the HARMONIE-AROME ACCORD enhancement will be to combine all-sky with VARBC and dynamical emissivity approach.

Figure 35. the mean (red) and standard deviation (green) of first-guess (solid) and analysis (dashed) departures for all-sky mhs channels 3,4,5 and the number of observations (black) for 01-10 sep 2019. Channels 1 and 2 are blacklisted in Harmonie-Arome.

To summarise, findings from both comparisons of HARMONIE-AROME model with observations (in section 3.3.2) and off-line simulation experiments (in section 3.3.3) have guided local adaptations of all-sky to the HARMONIE-AROME system that have been implemented in the full 3D-model all-sky framework. Substantial progress, in accordance with project plans has been made in the form of all-sky preparations of all-sky route for MHS, all-sky, screening of observations, activation of TELSEM Atlases, passive monitoring runs, some first cycled data assimilation experiments, in addition to the local adaptation mentioned. Plan within the framework of this project is to carry out further full scale data assimilation experiment in the all-sky framework with VARBC activated and to investigate the effect of introducing graupel in the RTTOV-SCATT interface and also the systematic differences found between all-sky model counterparts and observations. Our goal is as well to make use of real AWS data within the all-sky framework. Worth mentioning is as well that project results and enhancements regarding all-sky have been ported back to the reference HIRLAM cy46 version, to be used by the entire HIRLAM community.

3.4. Operational use of 325 GHz radiances

All-sky assimilation is in development inside the Nordic NWP systems (see above), but will not be ready for operational use until the launch of AWS. We have chosen not to devote resources to assimilate 325 GHz data in clear-sky mode. The receiver noise temperature at 325 GHz is higher than the one at 183 GHz, but theoretically there is still some additional information on humidity at 325 GHz. However, to also assimilate 325 GHz would require a mean to determine what 325 GHz footprints that can be considered as clear-sky, i.e. to develop a cloud filtering algorithm for these channels, but this is a very challenging task not worth the effort considering that all-sky assimilation is in the pipeline. On the other hand, simulations have shown that 325 GHz data offer a good basis for improving the cloud filtering of 183 GHz data (Kaur et al, 2021), and this possibility will be explored.

The cloud filtering algorithm to be developed will follow the approach explored in Eriksson et al. (2020) and Kaur et al. (2021). That is, the filtering approach will be based solely on AWS data, no

deviation to model equivalent, or background, will be needed. The basic idea is that 183 and 325 GHz channel antenna temperatures follow each other relatively closely for clear-sky, and deviations from this pattern is a direct indication on an impact of clouds. A presence of clouds gives a considerably higher impact at 325 GHz than at 183 GHz, up to a factor of 9 higher (occurs at Rayleigh conditions). Some basic considerations for the cloud filtering to apply for AWS:

- There will be a separate cloud filtering for 50 GHz and 183 GHz channels, following the present treatment of e.g. ATMS.
- The initial cloud filtering for 50 GHz channels will initially follow what is applied today for e.g. ATMS. Using 325 GHz data here is difficult due to technical reasons. Where the cloud filtering is applied, antenna temperatures are only at hand as single footprints. Accordingly, the 325 GHz data at hand cover only a part of the 50 GHz footprint and no safe cloud filtering can be offered. This would require access to 325 GHz data covering the full 50 GHz footprint.
- The 325 GHz data will be applied for cloud filtering of AWS channels 32 to 36 (176.311 to 182.311 GHz). The cloud filtering will work the best for these channels in falling order (i.e. best for AWS 36, Eriksson et al. (2020)).
- A first iteration of the algorithm will aim for a conservative filtering, without separation of the 183 GHz channels (i.e. the filtering results in all or nothing).
- Later iterations will aim for being less conservative (without a negative impact on forecasts) and allow a channel specific filtering. The latter is motivated by the fact that a lower cloud layer can have an impact on e.g. AWS 32 and 33, while the remaining 183 GHz channels can be considered as cloud free (as their response is limited to higher altitudes).

The cloud filtering algorithm will be developed at Chalmers with a first version ready in early spring 2024. The algorithm will be delivered as Python code. The implementation in the operational system will be made by HARMONIE-AROME researchers within the project. The operational code base, written in Fortran, has not yet any support for machine learning. This means that the algorithm to be developed must use standard regression or a very basic neural network structure that can be represented as a few matrix-vector operations. Cloud filtering using 325 GHz by regression was considered in Eriksson et al. (2020), and this work will be used as the starting point for the operational algorithm to be defined. A completely new set of radiative transfer simulations will be performed, to base the algorithm on latest data and knowledge and to obtain data representing the full swath of AWS.

4. Summary of AWS project HARMONIE-AROME enhancements and operational NWP

4.1. Overview of project achievements

Within this project the HARMONIE-AROME system has been prepared for use of observations from the MW instrument onboard the AWS satellite. In addition, there has been substantial work concerning general use of MW radiances from heritage sensors, and that will as well be beneficial

for assimilation of MW radiances from AWS. These developments have been summarised here. In addition we have evaluated the impact of various kinds of developments. Some of the developments were more short term and have already reached operations in MetCoOp and AROME-Arctic, like the dynamical emissivity approach for low peaking channels with special handling over sea-ice. These enhancements are presented in section 4.2, together with some results from pre-operational studies. The footprint operator applied to handle scale-differences between model and MW radiance observations has proven encouraging. There are however still some refinements regarding footprint representation and computational efficiency needed before operational use can be considered. Regarding use of MW low-peaking channels, there is on-going work regarding reflection assumptions over snow surfaces and derivation of enhanced emissivity estimates over snow and ice surfaces with optimal estimation theory. For both of these we aim for further assimilation studies within the HARMONIE-AROME modelling framework within the course of the project. Operational use within the time-frame of the project will be considered for refined surface reflections, while enhanced emissivity maps is a longer term future goal for HARMONIE-AROME.

A smaller fraction of the project has as well been devoted to preparing the HARMONIE-AROME system for use of MW observations both in clear and cloudy conditions (so called all-sky) and potential adaptations needed in the HARMONIE-AROME modelling system as well as in the radiative transfer modelling calculations and its interface. This work consisted in comparisons of HARMONIE-AROME short-range forecasts with ground based measurements of clouds and precipitation, off-line simulations with ARTS modelling system and full scale model simulations. The main outcome from these studies were that: 1) for HARMONIE-AROME it is important to include graupel in the interface to the radiative transfer calculations, 2) the radiative transfer calculations are dependent on the particle aggregate assumptions and the ones used by default in RTTOV versions used by HARMONIE-AROME and later versions seem to be appropriate and 3) there is no specific reason to mimic the HARMONIE-AROME snow model particle size distribution for radiative transfer simulations. Some first results of all-sky full model assimilation experiments, taking these findings into account, are aimed for within the time-frame of this project.

Finally, we have established a work plan and detailed strategy for use of 325 GHz radiances in the HARMONIE-AROME modelling system. The idea is to use it to filter out cloud and rain affected radiances, as a potential enhancement to the currently used cloud filter in the operational clear-sky data assimilation. Technical preparations will be carried out before the launch of the AWS and the methodology will be evaluated with real AWS data once they become available. A roadmap for developments carried out here but that have not yet reached operations is given in section 4.3.

4.2 Enhancements that have reached operations

During the course of the project several steps towards harmonisation of use of MW radiances among nordic NWP centres have been taken, compared to the situation summarised in Table 1. Since then Metop-A has been decommissioned and NOAA-20 ATMS as well as FY-3E MWHS-2 data have become available. There is some pre-operational work on use of FY-3E MWHS-2, but it has not yet reached operations at any operational nordic NWP centre. On the other hand, all operational nordic NWP centres have added NOAA-20 ATMS into operations. In addition there have been some harmonisations among use of Suomi-NPP ATMS and FY-3D MWHS-2. At project start there were some discrepancies in use of these instruments between nordic operational NWP centres, while today these data are used by all centres. The current operational use of satellite MW radiances at operational nordic NWP centres are shown in Table 5. The only remaining difference between centres regarding the use of instruments is that AROME-ARCTIC still does not make use of the NOAA-19 MHS instrument, like MetCoOp and DMI do.

Table 5. MW data usage in MetCoOp, AROME-ARCTIC and DMI operational DA (N18=NOAA-18, N19=NOAA-19, N20=NOAA-20, SNP=Suomi NPP, MB=Metop-B, MC=Metop-C, FY3D=FY-3D) at the production of ESA-AWS deliverable D2 (December, 2023).

	N18	N19	N20	SNP	MB	MC	FY3D	land/sea	land	open sea	Sea ice
AMSU-A	xxx	xxx			xxx	xxx		5-9,5-9,6-9	5-9,5-9	5-9, 5-9,6-9	5-9, 5-9,6-9
ATMS			xxx	xxx				6-10,18-22,5-9,17-22,6-10,19-22	6-10,19-22,2,7-9,17-22,6-10,19-22	6-10,18-22,5-9,17-22,6-10,19-22	6-10,18-22,7-9,17,6-10,19-22
MHS		xx			xxx	xxx		3-5, 3-5,3-5	3-5,3-5,3-5	3-5,3-5,3-5	3-5, 3-5,none
MWHS-2							xxx	11-15,11-15	11-15,11-14	11-15,11-15	11-15,11-15

There are also enhancements in use of surface sensitive channels from all instruments AMSU-A, ATMS, MHS and MWHS-2. Both MetCoOp and AROME-ARCTIC have introduced operationally use of low-peaking channels from these instruments over open sea, land and sea-ice, utilising the dynamical emissivity procedure introduced in this project. The new channels introduced are in accordance with Table 2, which also presents the window channels used for emissivity retrieval to achieve the emissivity of the current situation, as illustrated in Figure 3. The enhancements include dynamical emissivity approach with extrapolation special handling of 183 GHz frequency radiances over sea ice according to equation (3). The results from pre-operational studies preceding the operational introduction are presented in section 4.2.1 for MetCoOp and 4.2.2 for AROME-ARCTIC. For future DMI operational configurations, some studies have started for future pre-operational use, but it has not yet reached operations. It should be emphasised that with a dynamical emissivity approach the emissivities are derived for each individual assimilation cycle and satellite overpass, so that they are adaptively updated and no averaging is needed. Figure 36 illustrates the derived emissivities for AMSU-A channel 5 instrument onboard satellites passing 20210215 09 UTC, used in the data assimilation, and derived from the AMSU-A window channel 3. For reference also the emissivities that would have resulted from the old, previously used system are shown.

Figure 36. Instantaneous land surface emissivity maps for AMSU-A Channel 5 (53.6 GHz), as derived from channel 3 (50.3 GHz) and for 20210215 09 UTC. This is the way dynamical emissivity approach is used in nordic operational systems and is illustrated here for the MetCoOp domain.

4.2.2 MetCoOp pre-operational studies

Operational introduction of low-peaking channels using the dynamical emissivity approach in the MetCoOp operational NWP system was carried out in two steps. In the first step introduction of low-peaking channels from the MW instruments AMSU-A and MHS were evaluated and then introduced operationally on the 25th of January 2023. In the second step introduction of low-peaking channels from the MW instruments ATMS and MWHS-2 were evaluated and then introduced operationally on 19th April 2023. The operational introduction was for each step preceded by a parallel data assimilation and forecast impact tests. During these the currently operational system was compared with a system when the enhancements regarding low-peaking channels were added on top. The parallel experiments were for both steps carried out with archived data and for a winter period (three weeks during February 2022) and for a summer period (three weeks during June 2022).

Results are shown in Figure 37 for the effect of introducing low peaking channels of AMSU-A and MHS. Verification scores in the form of bias and standard deviation against radiosondes in the area are presented for temperature and specific humidity as a function of vertical level and averaged over forecast ranges up to 36 h. Scores are for forecasts launched from 00 and 12 UTC. Overall the impact of low-peaking channels from MHS and AMSU-A was found rather neutral, with some small positive effect on summertime humidity scores.

Figure 37. Vertical profiles of standard deviation and bias for temperature (left) and specific humidity (right) forecasts for winter (upper) and summer (lower) periods. Scores are averaged over forecast ranges from +0 to +36 hours. The scores are for verification against all radiosonde observations within the model domain and for periods in February and June 2022. Purple curves are for equivalents of operations and green curves for equivalents of operations after introduction of low peaking channels for AMSU-A and MHS instruments.

The effect of introducing low peaking channels of ATMS and MWHS-2, on top of the already introduced ones for AMSU-A and MHS, are illustrated in Figures 38 and 39. Figure 38 is for forecasts launched from 00 UTC and Figure 39 is for forecasts launched from 12 UTC. Verification scores shown are again in the form of bias and standard deviation against radiosondes in the area and are presented for temperature and specific humidity as a function of vertical level and averaged over forecast ranges up to 36 h. Overall the impact of low-peaking channels from MHS and AMSU-A was found rather neutral, with some small positive effect on summertime humidity scores. The effect on forecast verification scores on the newly introduced low peaking ATMS and MWHS-2 channels are rather neutral for temperature forecasts. However, a positive impact can be seen on low level specific humidity forecasts.

Figure 38. Vertical profiles of standard deviation and bias temperature (left) and specific humidity (right) forecasts for winter (upper) and summer (lower) periods. Scores are averaged over forecast ranges from +0 to +36 hours. The scores are for verification against all radiosonde observations within the model domain and for periods in February and June 2022. Purple curves are for equivalents of operations and green curves for equivalents of operations after introduction of low peaking channels for AMSU-A and MHS instruments.

Figure 39. Vertical profiles of standard deviation and bias temperature (left) and specific humidity (right) forecasts for winter (upper) and summer (lower) periods. Scores are averaged over forecast ranges from +0 to +36 hours. The scores are for verification against all radiosonde observations within the model domain and for periods in February and June 2022. Purple curves are for equivalents of operations and green curves for equivalents of operations after introduction of low peaking channels for AMSU-A and MHS instruments.

4.2.2 AROME-ARCTIC pre-operational studies

Dynamic emissivity has been used operationally for AMSU-A and MHS since 2018 in AROME-Arctic. In June 2022, ATMS and MWHS-2 radiances (including low-peaking channels) were activated in the operational suite of AROME-Arctic. Similarly to MetCoOP, both instruments have been added to the pre-operational suite first for validation purposes. Figures 40 and 41 show forecast impact of adding the low-peaking ATMS and MWHS-2 (with dynamic emissivity) channels on top of the full observing system compared to radiosondes. Results indicate a positive impact in terms of humidity (relative & specific) close to the surface, a rather neutral impact on temperature and a slightly negative impact on the wind speed.

Figure 40. Vertical profiles of standard deviation and bias specific humidity (left) and relative humidity (right) forecasts for spring periods. Scores are averaged over forecast ranges from +0 to +36 hours. The scores are for verification against all radiosonde observations within the model domain and for periods March and April 2022. Purple curves are for equivalents of operations (with ATMS & MWHS-2) and green curves for equivalents of operations after introduction of low peaking channels and dynamic emissivity.

Figure 41. Same as Figure 40 but for temperature (left) and wind speed (right).

4.3 Roadmap for further developments

4.3.1 Future of HIRLAM and nordic operational centres

The HIRLAM project has a main functionality to provide quality assured limited area modelling systems operational systems for operational use. These systems are based on developments within the ACCORD system and in a modelling framework in common with ECMWF. At the end of 2025 the HIRLAM consortium will not exist in its current form any longer. The operational centres within the HIRLAM consortium will then merge into one common operational modelling centre called United Weather Centers, UWC. These include MetCoOp, UWC-W and also the Spanish weather service AEMET. The idea is that UWC will manage the functionalities of HIRLAM. The formation of UWC will harmonise priorities, infrastructure etc between different nordic operational centres and thereby among other things remove the remaining minor differences in use of MW radiances.

4.3.2 Roadmap for developments stimulated by ESA AWS project

Considerable progress regarding use of MW radiances has been achieved in the ESA AWS project. The research that has not yet reached operations will be included in the ACCORD and HIRLAM development roadmaps. These developments include (1) reflection assumptions for low peaking channels over various surfaces, (2) use of AWS 325 GHz MW radiances for cloud detection, (3) use of footprint operators for various MW instruments and (4) all-sky assimilation of MW radiances.

Investigation and improvement of the Specular surface reflection assumption has recently not received so much attention in ACCORD and HIRLAM. The current project and its focus on low MW peaking channels and its focus on nordic winter conditions provided a great opportunity to continue the research started by Guedj et al. (2010). Here we activated in the AWS modelling branch a Lambertian reflection assumption and compared with the current default specular reflection. Encouraging results were found over snow covered surfaces. However, it was found that the modelling system needs to be more general to handle both a combination of reflection assumptions over one particular type of surface and also different kinds of reflections over various surface types. The work started here and associated results have been reported back to HIRLAM and ACCORD. The ACCORD HIRLAM roadmap includes the introduction of the functionality of combined reflection assumption. A first step will be to explore the code in the two future modelling cycles (cy46 and cy48), to see how ECMWF have evolved the framework with respect to reflection assumptions. Based on findings of status in these modelling cycles, actions will be taken to, within the timeframe of one to two years, have such functionalities ready for operational use.

Regarding use of AWS 325 GHz MW radiances for cloud detection, we aim to already within the time-frame of this project have a methodology for that ready for operational use. Our aim is to introduce it operationally together with operational use of AWS data, within the time frame of one year. The developments will be fed back from the AWS branch to the common ACCORD ECMWF modelling system.

The use of a footprint operator for MW will continue within the ACCORD modelling system. In the coming 4-5 years, the source code implementation and related developments will be focusing on the following aspects: Beyond the representation of IFOV, the wide beam i.e., the area where 95% of the energy comes from and the effective area swept by the instrument will be represented in the next version of the radiance footprint operator (within 1 year timeframe). Such a footprint operator requires increased computational costs, therefore, the optimisation is key to consider a future operational implementation. Mainly, the optimisation means coarser sampling resolution in the footprint operator averaging model equivalents after the RTTOV calls or testing “cheaper” approaches when the model information is aggregated before the RTTOV simulations (approximately in the coming 1-2 years). The implemented microwave radiance footprint operator will be tested in an all-sky framework as well taking into account the mixed cloud and precipitation conditions inside the FOV area, however, it is foreseen as a long-term goal in the ACCORD modelling system (in a 4-5 years time frame probably). Additionally, a completely different approach using Machine Learning algorithms is planned to be explored in order to eliminate the representation error in data assimilation. It can provide a fast and affordable solution to improve satellite assimilation in high-resolution NWP systems (4-5 years and beyond). The technical progress and implementation will be done in each upcoming HARMONIE-AROME cycles (cy46, cy49, and beyond) but the most mature implementation will be delivered in cy49.

Despite the relatively small resources available in this project for all-sky MW preparations some important steps have been taken and we have prepared for an increased ACCORD HIRLAM momentum in the all-sky work. In this project we have confirmed the suitability of HARMONIE-AROME cloud microphysics for an all-sky approach. We have also prepared the RTTOV-SCATT interface to HARMONIE-AROME physics and suggested appropriate settings for

RTTOV-SCATT snow particle size distributions as well as snow habit parameterisations. In addition, some first full-scale functionality tests of all-sky assimilation of MW radiances from the MHS instrument have been carried out. Most importantly the developments have been fed back as an option in the coming HIRLAM cy46-version of the reference system. This provides the opportunity for more researchers to take part in the all-sky work and corporate on it. At present a Norwegian team is making extensive tests on the performance and potential of all-sky in cy46. One area of improvement needed is to ensure that proper all-sky satellite data thinning procedures exist in the HARMONIE-AROME framework. An alternative to cy46 would be to proceed with the developments in cy49, available for more extensive experimentation within approximately a year, and port the findings of this project into cy49. It is still an open question to be further investigated if all-sky can provide some benefit with the currently operational 3D-Var assimilation methodology. Most likely benefit is larger with flow-dependent assimilation methods like 4D-Var, 3D-EnVar or hybrid variational ensemble methods. Such assimilation methods are currently in the process of being tested and/or introduced operationally at some ACCORD member states. All-sky will receive increased attention within the coming years and the aim is an operational use within 1-3 years from now.

5. List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
3D-Var	3-dimensional variational assimilation scheme
4D-Var	4-dimensional variational assimilation scheme
ACCORD	A Consortium for Convection-Scale Modeling Research and Development. A further collaboration between Meteo-France and the HIRLAM and ALADIN consortia.
ACL	Auto-correlation length
AIREP	Aircraft observations
ALADIN	Aire Limitée Adaptation dynamique Développement InterNational Development collaboration between Central and East European Countries.
AMV	Atmospheric Motion Vectors
AMSU-A	Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit-A
AROME	Application of Research to Operations at Mesoscale
ARPEGE	Action de Recherche Petite Echelle Grande Echelle
ARTS	Atmosphere Radiative Transfer Simulator
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
ATLAS	Monthly emissivity dataset
ATMS	Advanced Technology Microwave Sounder
AWS	Arctic Weather Satellites

BATOR	Observation pre-processing system for HARMONIE-AROME
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasting
EFOV	Effective FOV
EPS-SG	EUMETSAT Polar System-Second Generation
ESA	European Space Agency
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FASTEM	Fast Microwave Emissivity Model
FOV	Field-of-view
GPM	Global Precipitation Measurement
GMI	GPM Microwave Imager
HARMONIE	HIRLAM ALADIN Research on Mesoscale Operational NWP In Europe – convective-scale forecasting system
HA ESA	HARMONIE-AROME Evans Snow Aggregate
HA LPA	HARMONIE-AROME Large Plate Aggregate
HIRLAM	High Resolution Limited Area Modelling
IASI	Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer

ICI	Ice Cloud Imager
IFOV	Instantaneous FOV
IFS	Integrated Forecasting System
IR	Infra Red
LPA	Large Plate Aggregate
LSS	Liu Sector Snowflake
MetCoOp	Operational Collaboration between Sweden, Norway, Finland and the Baltic States.
Metop	Meteorological Operational Satellite Program of Europe
MGD	Modified Gamma Distribution
MHS	Microwave Humidity Sounder
MWHS2	MicroWave Humidity Sounder-2
MW	MicroWave
MWI	MircoWave Imager
MWS	MicroWave Sounder
NETCDF	Network Common Data Form
NOAA-POES	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - Polar Operational Environmental Satellites
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction
NWPSAF	NWP Satellite Application Facility

ODB	Observation DataBase
OMB	Observation minus Background
OSE	Observing System Experiment
OSSE	Observing System Simulation Experiment
OSTIA	Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Ice Analysis
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
RMSE	Root mean square error
RO	Radio Occultation
RTTOV	Radiative Transfer for TOVS
RTTOV-SCATT	Scattering package of the RTTOV
SMEAR	Station for measuring Ecosystem-Atmosphere Relations
SMRT	Snow microwave radiative transfer
Suomi-NPP/JPSS	Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership/Joint Polar Satellite System
SURFEX	Surface Externalisée
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
SWC	Snow Water Content
TELSEM	Tool to Estimate Land Surface Emissivity from Microwave to Submillimeter Waves
TEMP	Radiosonde observations
TIROS	Television Infrared Observation Satellite
TOVS	TIROS Operational Vertical Sounder

UWC-West	United Weather Centers West Operational Collaboration between Ireland, Denmark, Netherlands, and Iceland
VARBC	Variational Bias Correction

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